

Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana of Livelihood Skill Enhancement in Jharkhand

Pawan Kumar

Research Scholar, University Department of Commerce and Business Management Ranchi University, Ranchi

Corresponding Author - Dr. Jagruti M. Thumar

Email: thumar.jm@gmail.com

Abstract:

The skill development growth in the Jharkhand has witnessed rapid momentum in the past years. State has focused on opening relatively large size centres along with longer duration courses with focus on soft skills and OJT/Apprenticeship components. State government has also partnered with many agencies to set up skill development centres within college premises as well as many other premises to improve the employability of the youth of the state. Government has initiated skill development focused on Industry in partnership with leading global companies like Siemens and many more. As it is gaining scale and maturity, need for Skills Policy that weaves together all aspects in a comprehensive roadmap was acutely felt. This policy is being released at an opportune time and will enable rapid growth and improved outcomes for skill development and entrepreneurship interventions in the state especially for the youth. Government of Jharkhand is committed to enabling growth of the state through skilling the youth. A skilled and high productivity manpower base is a critical enabler in the growth of manufacturing, services and agriculture. It is also a critical intervention to harness the potential of 'Demographic Dividend' in a youthful state like Jharkhand. To give impetus to growth with scale, speed and standard, Government of Jharkhand has decided to frame a Skills Policy for the state of Jharkhand. This policy will be known as 'Jharkhand Skills Policy' and will be in force in the state.

Human factor is the key to the developmental process. For our economy to grow fast, a skilled workforce is essential and for economic development to be equitable it is necessary to incorporate the vast major portion of the population living in rural areas. India has a vast geographic dividend. According to census 2011, India has 55 million potential workers between the age group of 15-35 years in rural areas. Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana (DDU-GKY), a part of the National Rural Livelihood Mission (NRLM), has been started with the objective of improving the economic condition of rural poor. It aims to satisfy the livelihood ambitions of youth residing in rural areas by training them and providing employment opportunities. This paper focuses on the Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana and highlights its significance in increasing rural employment in the state of Jharkhand. Secondary data has been used for the purpose of study.

Keywords: Rural Development, Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana, National Rural Livelihood Mission, Rural Poor, Employment.

Introduction:

"If we have to promote the development of our country then our mission has to be 'skill development' and 'Skilled India'. We have to create a pool of young people who can be entrepreneurs as well as job providers while those who does not have means to create job, can success over their counter parts in the world possessing high competency and skills. Today, Jharkhand is one of the youngest states in the country with more than 57% of its 3.3 crore population in the working age group of 15-59 years and around 70% below 35 years of age.

Being a recently formed independent State, Jharkhand faces peculiar economic and demographic challenges too. More than 75% of the population lives in rural areas and about 38% people belong to Marginalized section groups. On other hand, Jharkhand is a mineral rich state and has tremendous

wealth of natural resources. Skill development interventions need to match jobs to skilling, generate wage premium, provide career paths through up skilling, re-skilling and recognition of prior learning and generate sustainable livelihood. It is imperative that the state benefits from demographic dividend potential. This is possible only through very well conceptualized policies and strategic roadmaps along with effective on the ground implementation of various interventions. It is critical that state government has policies, processes, procedures, innovation and technology as part of an effective implementation plan. This policy sets the bedrock of the very ambitious and critical task before us.

Skill Development is one of the most important focus areas of the Government. Government has committed to provide attractive and

sustainable livelihood opportunities for youth. In this context, this policy is going to be a very important milestone. This policy will give right direction to improve the quality and quantity of jobs being offered to youth. Government focus will strongly remain on engaging with local industries and incubate barefoot entrepreneurship enterprises to provide livelihood opportunities to the youth of the state and this will significantly reduce unattractive and distress migration of the youth. Jharkhand Skill Development Mission Society is releasing “State Skill Policy” with lots of innovation and interventions which would be welcomed over coming years.

Skill development is at the cornerstone of all developmental activities of the Government of Jharkhand and it is an integral part of “Momentum Jharkhand”. Higher education and skill development in Jharkhand is undergoing significant changes towards bridging the skill gap. The policy has very rigorously identified key challenges of the state. Based on vigorous analysis of existing skill gap, youth aspiration will be further matched towards demand for jobs/self employment/ barefoot entrepreneurship opportunities etc. With this policy Jharkhand Government is providing a stimulus to the skilling ecosystem in the state and its contribution to Skill India Mission. Through integrating vocational education in our secondary and higher secondary educational system; we are making every effort to employability of youth. Initiatives like mega skill centres, centre of excellence, technical education institutions and skill universities will ensure horizontal and vertical mobility pathways in education system. Towards fulfillment of all these initiatives and goals, Government of Jharkhand has set up Jharkhand Skill Development Mission Society in the year of 2013 which is currently working under the Department of Higher, Technical Education and Skill Development, Government of Jharkhand. The society will be the flag bearer of all proposed initiatives under Jharkhand Skill Development Policy 2017. I foresee a bright future for the youth of Jharkhand who choose to join Mission Skill India and reap the benefits proposed in the policy document.

The Jharkhand Skill Development Mission is committed to improve the skilling ecosystem in the state and is the apex body responsible for all skill development activities, policies and programs within the State. It acts as the convergence platform for all other departments as well. The JSMD is determined to bring a robust up-liftment in skill development sector and is progressively working towards meeting their target of skilling 20 lakh people in the next five years, as it can be derived from their current and planned initiatives. One of the flagship initiatives undertaken by the Mission is the

development of a policy on skill development for the state to address issues confronting state specific challenges for skill development, such as, industry-market symmetry, exclusion of marginalized groups, limited vertical/horizontal pathways between skills and formal education, raising profile of skills and making it aspirational for the youth and so on. This policy is centered on four main themes of developing capacity to match demand for skilled workforce; identifying and opening high potential sectors for economic growth and innovation; building and sustaining competencies for future labour market needs and convergence across schemes. A well-educated, skilled and motivated population will contribute to economic progress; promote greater equality and social inclusion in our society, as well as enhancing Jharkhand’s national and international reputation. The quality of outcomes are ensured by compliance to National Skill Quality Framework as well as collaborating with foreign education institutions to ensure skilling of youth to National and International standards. The progress on the implementation of this policy will be measured against the achievement of expected outcomes as well as creation of a competent workforce who would be appreciated as an asset by various industries. This progress will be measured through a variety of mechanisms including the Mission’s Annual Report.

Human factor is the key to the developmental process. Human Resource Development is a holistic concept which aims at identifying the vast potential hidden within the people and sharpening them through training so as to make them aware of their capabilities and utilise it to the fullest for their overall growth and advancement. The process encompasses development of their proficiencies by providing them such environment which enables them to make their competencies as core competencies and thereby improve their current scenario and contribute in the development of the entire nation. constitutes about 70% of the country’s total population. For development to be equitable it is necessary to incorporate the vast major portion of the population living in rural areas.

India being a land of villages, rural population Keeping this in view the government of India; in order to include the rural poor in the process of growth and development, has launched many schemes for training them, thus improving their skills so that they can earn their livelihood.

Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana :

Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana (DDU-GKY) is a part of the National Rural Livelihood Mission (NRLM) launched on 25th September 2014. This programme exclusively concentrates on rural youth between the

age group of 15 to 35 years from underprivileged families. This programme supports the Skill India Movement of the government and thereby works in a direction to improve the socio- economic condition of the poor residing in rural areas.

As per the government data, more than 180 million youth in the nation among the age group of 18 to 34 years are living in villages. According to census 2011, India has 55 million potential workers between the age group of 15-35 years in rural areas. A very big skill gap has been recognised by The National Policy for Skill Development & Entrepreneurship 2015. It has estimated that there will be a skill gap of about 109.73 million in 24 significant divisions by the year 2022. This gap in skill cannot be filled if the country does not focus on the 55 million youth residing in rural part of the country. An article published in 2013 in FICCI and Ernst – Young also highlighted that there will be a scarcity of more than 47 million competent personnel throughout the world by the year 2020. Thus it becomes imperative for the country to train its rural youth population and place them in jobs across the world and realize its demographic dividend.

DDU-GKY works in a public private partnership mode. Through its partners it provides skill training to the people and supports the national policies and programmes on skill development. The partners are encouraged to come up with novel ideas to maintain a balance between knowledge and capability. DDU-GKY has a skilling environment and a distinctive arrangement of conditions in which the training partners involved are dedicated to alter and improve the lives of people. The partners involved are experts in their areas that strive to add value to the lives of rural poor. Under this programme, the partners are supported through investment, ability building, policies for retaining, associations for global employment and technology support for training purposes. The scope of DDU-GKY is very broad and at present this programme is being implemented across 21 States and UTs, 568 districts, and over 6,215 blocks providing livelihood opportunities to the youth. Currently

under this programme more than 690 projects have been implemented involving over 300 associations, in more than 330 professions from 82 business sectors.

As per data the number of trained candidates have exceeded a number of around 2.7 lakh and over 1.34 lakh candidates have been employed in different jobs in the course of the last financial year. Since 2012, DDU-GKY till date have made an investment of over INR 5,600 Crores addressing the employment issue of the rural youth throughout the country.

Features of Ddu-Gky:

- Impart skill training to rural poor free of cost according to market demand.
- Proper attention focussed on socially underprivileged group (SC/ST 50%/Minority 15%/Women 33%).
- Implementation through Project Implementation Agencies (PIAs) in Public Private Partnership mode.
- Shifting importance from training to career progression.
- Providing better support to placed candidates, both before during and after placement.
- Providing guaranteed jobs to at least 75% candidates.
- Enhancing the capacity of implementation partners.
- Special focus in special areas like Jammu & Kashmir.
- Regular monitoring of attendance through biometric system.

Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Grameen Kaushalya Yojana (DDU-GKY) is one of the biggest programmes sponsored by the government to impart skill training in the country. Table 1 depicts the details of number of persons trained and placed under DDU-GKY, number of training providers, training partners, and training centres, sectors covered and job roles offered in the year 2015-16.

Training Details under DDU-GKY in 2020-21.

Particulars	Numbers
Trained	2,70,329
Placed	1,34,744
Number of Partners	315
Number of Projects	697
Number of Training Centres	1096
Sectors Covered	85
Job-Roles Covered	330

Ddu-Gyk in the State of Jharkhand State:

Jharkhand is the 16th largest state in terms of population (2,55,45,198, Census 2011), with its rural population constituting 76.75 % of the total

Pawan Kumar

population. The importance of skill development in supporting rural development cannot be neglected. In order to provide better prospects for the human resources residing in rural areas, the State

Government under the Department of Panchayat and Rural Development (prd.cg.gov.in) is implementing various programmes for their training and skill development. Government of India under the Ministry of Rural Development have started DDU-GYK programme to provide employment oriented skill training to rural under privileged youth. It works in a Public Private Partnership (PPP) mode, where the training partners submit their proposal for various skill training projects. The government after scrutinising the projects invests in them and generate a cordial and healthy environment with complete technical support. All these efforts ensure that a quality training programme is being created and a quality training is being offered to the rural beneficiaries.

It has established a structure and a procedure which has set a standard in the world thereby enabling rural under privileged youth to get access to quality training programme and an employment opportunity to change their present socio-economic condition.

Significance of Ddu-Gyk In Jharkhand:

The state of Jharkhand has a vast unexplored potential to generate over two lakh jobs in structured as well as in a muddled manner. This supports the report of Associated Chambers of Commerce and Industry of India (Assocham). Under DDU- GYK, the Govt. of Jharkhand. provides opportunity for livelihood training only to unemployed rural men and women.

All training under the scheme is provided free of cost to the registered candidates. Under residential training mode, along with training, free lodging and boarding facility is given to the candidates or otherwise travelling allowance is given to them. Training materials like pen, pencil, notebook, book etc along with uniform is also distributed free of cost to candidates. Apart from imparting trade and livelihood related training, candidates are also given opportunity to learn and improve English communication skills, develop their personality. An important feature of this programme is that, training sessions are arranged in fully equipped labs with latest technologies. Candidates on completion of training get certificates. The govt. ensures that candidates after completing their training programme are being offered a minimum job of Rs 6000/- p.m.

Conclusion:

Govt of Jharkhand is playing a crucial role in skill development schemes for the youth of the state. Govt policy for the same is very good, they have very good roadmap. Jharkhand is committed to provide better skill development for all and the concerted efforts of the government have resulted in the state to increase its skilled rate quite impressively over the years. Govt has made significant strides in improving the quality of its skill development infrastructure during the last few

years and planning for future also. This is in line with the statement of the state which says, "Skilling the youth of the state through better skill development policy for better development of the state. Skill development plays an important role in enhancing the capability of the people and in promoting human resource development for better availability of skilled manpower to the state. To create a high performing skill development and barefoot entrepreneurship ecosystem aligned with national and international standards. The State is committed to skilling of 20 lakh youths from across the varied geographies of Jharkhand by 2022 through establishing robust institutional mechanisms and developing state of the art training infrastructure.

The livelihood colleges are now working to make rural youth in the state of Jharkhand more skilled by offering such training courses. A number of livelihood colleges have been opened in the state to mould the raw talent of youths in a well- defined form. Career fairs are being organised to increase awareness among the rural youth, and they can get knowledge of the different livelihood and career options available to them. The youth can now increase their empowerment by claiming the right to skill development. All these steps taken by state government to set up a milestone of success towards skill development is now providing positive results.

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